

“APPLICATION OF QR CODES IN THE STATE MUSEUM OF APPLIED ART OF UZBEKISTAN: REVITALISATION OF NATIONAL MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS THROUGH TECHNOLOGY”

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the process of creation and application of QR codes in the State Museum of Applied Art of Uzbekistan. It is known that QR codes with the use of audio guides were applied before, but for listening to the national musical instruments (exhibits) it was required to create additional QR codes, in which the melodies of musical instruments were placed.

Keywords: QR code, museum, exhibit, audio guide, multimedia, history, heritage, art, visitor, culture, digital technologies.

With the development of modern innovative technologies it is possible to observe how the use of QR codes has been popularized in museums, having scanned which visitors can use audio guides or video materials. Audio guides in museums are an important tool allowing visitors to get detailed information about the exhibited works of art, historical objects and collections. Traditionally, visitors received information by reading written descriptions next to museum exhibits. Today, however, audio guides integrated with QR codes make the museum visit more impressive and interactive.

There are many benefits of using QR codes in museums, the use of QR code audio guides offer visitors a special experience [1]. Visitors who scan the QR code next to each exhibit can listen to a detailed audio explanation. This provides visitors with a more complete narrative and allows them to have a personal experience while learning the details of the museum's exhibit. The introduction of QR codes into the space of museums in the country can serve as an important factor in saving time: listening to an audio guide by scanning QR codes becomes an alternative method of reading written descriptions and receiving information [2]. Quick and efficient delivery of information allows visitors to spend more time in the museum to see more exhibits. By generating a QR code with information, the audio guide can be used for multilingual communication. Audio guides with QR codes give the opportunity to provide information in different languages. Foreign tourists visiting the museum can listen to audio explanations in their languages by scanning QR codes (mainly audio explanations in English, French, German) [3]. This experience provides the

development of a multicultural structure in the museum. When creating audio explanations there is a problem of translation into Chinese, Korean, Spanish and other languages.

The main purpose of QR code audio guides is to provide more detailed information about the exhibits. Information placards are usually limited in providing information, but audio guides can offer a wider range of explanations in familiarising visitors with an exhibit. By scanning QR codes, visitors can access a more comprehensive set of information and better understand the history of the exhibit [4].

The State Museum of Applied Art of Uzbekistan is filled with visitors from all over the world every year. The museum is rich in exhibits expressing the national culture and art of the Uzbek people. The number of foreign visitors is sometimes so large that the museum staff, who speak foreign languages, do not always have time to promptly answer all the questions and provide the necessary information to each of them. In order to improve the quality of visitors' service special signs with QR codes leading to audio guides with information about the museum were installed at the entrance, near the ticket office. The audio guide familiarises visitors with the museum's activities in 3 languages: Uzbek, Russian and English.

The State Museum of Applied Arts of Uzbekistan, the Agency of Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan (the organisation was split and reorganised from: Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan) and the French company "Orpheo" worked on the creation of audio guides.

Since 1992, "Orpheo" [5] has been a leading provider of modern technologies for organising tours in museums, exhibitions, parks and other tourist sites. This company offers innovative solutions including mobile applications, audio guides, radio guides, content development (including VR and AR), as well as organising audio guide services. "Orpheo" is one of the leading international companies with branches in 12 countries, having produced more than 350 thousand devices and more than 400 applications used by millions of visitors every year. "Orpheo's" main activities can be categorised into several types:

- production of equipment (audio guides, multimedia guides, radio guides, proximity headphones);
- production of multimedia content (audio, video, images, 3D, VR/AR, etc.);

- software development (iOS/Android mobile applications, PWA applications, remote device management systems);
- organisation and management of turnkey audio guide service;
- design and installation of audio-visual installations.

Many museums around the world have long ago started to install high-sensitivity sensor audio guides near exhibits, which can be used to broadcast both information materials and musical accompaniment. The museums of Uzbekistan, especially the State Museum of Applied Art of Uzbekistan, have an acute problem of supplementing the exposition with special modern equipment. Due to insufficient funding Uzbek museums cannot afford many modern technologies, there is an opportunity to improve the functioning audio guide in the museum by adding QR codes.

As Uzbek national musical instruments are of great interest to foreign visitors, the author of the article has developed special QR codes with the help of which it is possible to listen to melodies performed on these instruments. Creation of QR codes is a unique solution of this problem. To use QR codes a visitor will not need any additional equipment, except for his own mobile device to scan the code and to hear how the national musical instrument chosen by him sounds. To scan a QR code of the exhibit with the help of a smartphone it is necessary to use the internet. For a long time the workers of the museum have been experiencing inconveniences of demonstration of the national musical instrument chosen by foreign visitors, showing them by means of manual search at the platform 'YouTube'. The generated QR code is systematised for each national musical instrument separately and works on the automated form when scanned by a person's smartphone (mobile device). To date, this experience plays an important role in improving the activity of museums in Uzbekistan and contributes to attracting the attention of foreign visitors from all over the world. The created QR codes for Uzbek national musical instruments serve as an additional application for audio guides, which are already available in the museum space.

The uniqueness of creating and installing QR codes is that their content can be constantly updated or supplemented - for example, when adding new exhibits to the museum collection or receiving new information about the existing ones. In this case QR codes and the content information is completely updated and generated anew. This way of appliance of modern digital technologies allows always providing the visitors with the most actual and accurate information. The staff of the State Museum of Applied Art of Uzbekistan on a constant basis

collects and processes information on the history and development of applied art in the country. An interactive screen has been installed in the large hall of the museum to show videos on the development of applied arts in the country. In the future, to enrich the multimedia content of the museum, the collected materials can be processed using special graphic programmes and new video resources can be created for demonstration to visitors. These video materials can also be embedded into QR codes so that visitors could scan them with their smartphones and view them.

Creation and use of QR codes is not limited only to viewing information materials - with their help it is also possible to collect and analyse data on visitors. Scanning each QR code allows tracking the number of visitors and the popularity of exhibits, which makes it possible to collect statistics on people interested in the museum's activity. The received data provide valuable information for further planning and improvement of the museum's activity. The use of audio guides with QR codes offers visitors a more impressive, interactive and personalised experience. Visitors save time and explore the museum in more depth, learning more about the artefacts.

QR code audio guides combine the benefits of technology with art, culture and history. This method allows museums to reach a wider audience, make it easier for visitors to obtain information and make the time spent in the museum more efficient.

In the digital age, it is particularly important for museums to remain relevant and actively engage in promotion. Museums are first and foremost 'living' knowledge, which no digital technologies can replace, but certainly the museum space must adapt to modern conditions, which are constantly changing and expanding. New digital technologies of the modern museum world cannot fully ensure the authenticity and preservation of cultural heritage, but they can significantly expand its information potential and enhance its accessibility properties.

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